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Activated Carbon Preparation and Physicochemical Characterization from Plantain Peduncle and Raphia Palm Nut for Sorption Application

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ABSTRACT

Activated carbon was produced from plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*) peduncle (PP) and raphia palm (*Raphia hookeri*) nut (RPN) by alkali activation. The precursors were carbonized for 30 minutes in a vecstar furnace at 700 °C. It was chemically activated for 60 minutes in a vecstar furnace at a temperature of 400 °C with 0.5 M sodium hydroxide (NaOH). The activated carbon (AC) was treated with 0.5 M ethanoic acid and washed with distilled water until the pH reached 6.73 and 7, respectively for PP and RPN, and were heated in an oven at 110 °C until dried. The activated carbon produced was characterized based on moisture content (7.5%), ash content (4.25%) volatile matter (62.2%), bulk density (0.84 g/mL), pore volume (1.7 cm³), porosity (6.01cm⁶/g), fixed carbon (26.05%), pH (6.8), iodine number (320.41 mg/g) and saponification value (78.53 mg/g) for PP. Physicochemical properties for RPN were moisture content (2.5%), ash content (8.25%), volatile matter (32.25%), bulk density (0.84 g/cm³), pore volume (3.1 cm³), and porosity (1.47 cm⁶/g). The results were compared with ASTM specification and were found to fall within the specified range. Thus, activated carbon produced from plantain peduncle and raphia palm nuts can be used as adsorbents for effluent treatment and other contaminants' remediation.

Keywords: Activated carbon, Plantain peduncle, Raphia palm nut, activation, characterization,

INTRODUCTION

Activated carbon (AC) is a class of solid materials derived from the processing of carbonaceous substances. They present properties of a highly developed internal surface area and porosity, which make them effective adsorbents (Tarikuzzaman, 2023, Ganjoo et al., 2023). The surface area of activated carbon typically ranges from **450 to 3,000 m²/g**, depending on the source material and activation process (Ganjoo et al., 2023, Wikipedia contributors, 2025). Nanoporous carbons with a BET area of 4800 m²g⁻¹ have also been reported (Chalmpes et al., 2024). The pore sizes in activated carbon are categorized into micropores (<2 nm), mesopores (2–50 nm), and macropores (>50 nm) (De Oliveira et al., 2021). The specific diameter range varies based on the material and application. The range of these properties drawing from the internal surface area, porosity and pore sizes, make activated carbon versatile for applications like water purification, air filtration, and other industrial processes (Gawande & Kaware, 2017). Activated carbon derived from plantain tree parts has been extensively studied for its

physicochemical properties and applications. The activation process, often involving chemical agents like phosphoric acid, significantly enhances its surface area and adsorption capacity.

Plantain peel-derived AC has been used for the removal of cassava wastewater contaminants (Onawumi et al., 2024), where some of the physicochemical parameters determined included biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), Chemical oxygen demand (COD), cyanide, and total dissolved solids (TDS). Ogbodo et al., (2021), prepared, characterized plantain peels AC which was modified by acetylation and used for adsorption of crude oil from contaminated water. Proximate properties such as fixed carbon and surface area of the raw peel powder were greater enhanced through carbonization and activation.

Coconut shell and plantain peel were used to produce activated carbon bio-activated with lemon juice and potash leached from the peel of unripe plantain which were used for dye adsorption (Efeovbokhan et al., 2019). The bio-activated AC was physically characterized for variables such as bulk density and yield, and microscopically with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) for surface morphology.

Plantain peel-activated carbon functionalized with iron oxide (Fe_2O_3) for H_2S adsorption was reported (Gbangbo et al., 2023); as well as activated carbon derived from ripe plantain peels (PPAC) for carbon dioxide (CO_2) capture activated using H_3PO_4 (Khama et al., 2024). PPAC was extensively characterized with SEM, XRD and FTIR. The performance of plantain peel-activated carbon in adsorbing selected heavy metals was carried out by Idowu (2015). The plantain peel-derived AC was characterized physically, for moisture content, ash content, bulk density, pH and surface area, and instrumentally with Fourier Transform Infrared Analysis (FTIR) and Neutron Activation Analysis (NAA). Activation was with H_3PO_4 , NaOH and ZnCl_2 .

Activated carbon derived from plantain peduncle (fruit stalk) has also been studied for its physicochemical and adsorptive properties (Ekpete et al., 2017). The AC was activated with H_3PO_4 and ZnCl_2 : physical characterization was done with respect to moisture content, ash content, bulk density, volatile matter and surface area, while instrumental characterization was with FTIR.

The endocarp of the Raphia palm nut is another promising precursor for activated carbon. Studies show that it can achieve high carbon yield, low ash content, and a large surface area when activated using chemical agents like H_3PO_4 and CaCl_2 (Ayoola et al., 2022). These properties make it suitable for applications such as solid adsorption refrigeration and the removal of organic and inorganic pollutants (Iwar, 2022). The activation process significantly enhances its adsorption efficiency, demonstrating its potential as an eco-friendly and cost-effective material.

This study is intended to add value to the stock of knowledge on the plantain peduncle and raphia palm nut activated carbon by means of another activating agent not yet used in the previous works examined.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection and Preparation of Unmodified Biomass

Plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*) peduncle (PP) and raphia palm (*Raphia hookeri*) nut (RPN) were respectively collected from Amassoma and Sagbama forest in Bayelsa State of Nigeria. The unmodified samples were diced, washed and sun-dried for 8 days and then oven-dried at a temperature of 75°C for 10 days to obtain a steady mass. They were then ground to fine size.

Carbonization: Carbonization was achieved by placing a known mass each of the biomass samples in a Vecstar furnace at 700°C for 30 minutes. The weights of the carbonized materials were 651 g PP and 238 g RPN.

Activation: Chemical activation was carried out with 0.5 M NaOH solution. The NaOH solution was poured into a container and a known mass of the carbonized samples were introduced into the solution and stirred for 5 minutes and left to stand for 12 hours. The NaOH solution was decanted, and the carbonized samples were placed in a Vecstar furnace at 400°C for 60 minutes. The chemically activated carbon was washed with 0.5 M acetic acid solution and rinsed thoroughly with distilled water until the pH were 6.73 for PP and 7 for RPN and dried in the oven at 110°C . The activated and non-activated carbon samples were ground to fine size and sieved with 0.30 mm mesh size and stored in an air-tight container for further work.

Physical Characterization Methods

Moisture Content: Preheated, cooled, clean and weighed crucibles were used for this analysis. Each sample weighing 2.00 g was put into the crucibles and placed in a hot air oven at 105°C for 3 hours in duplicate to obtain constant weight. The percent moisture content was determined using equation 1.

$$M_c = \frac{(C - D)g}{(C - A)g} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where: C = crucible mass + Preheated sample mass(g)
 D = crucible mass + Post-heated sample mass (g)
 A = crucible mass(g)

Ash Content: 2.00 g of each sample was put into the crucibles and transferred into vecstar furnace set at a temperature of 650°C. Samples were kept in the furnace for one hour, then cooled in a desiccator. The crucible and the contents were reweighed to ascertain the ash content through weight loss. The percent ash content was calculated from the equation 2

$$A_c = \left(\frac{D - A}{C - A} \right) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where: C = crucible mass + Preheated sample mass(g)
 D = crucible mass + Post-heated sample mass (g)
 A = crucible mass(g)

Volatile Matter Content: 1 g of each sample (activated and non-activated) was placed in a crucible and heated to 800 °C for 10 minutes in a Vecstar furnace. The crucible and the contents were cooled in a desiccator, and weighed twice. The volatile matter content on dry basis in percent (%) was obtained using equation 3

$$v_d = \left(\frac{100(C - D) - M_c(C - A)}{(C - A)(100 - M_c)} \right) \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Where: C = crucible mass + Preheated sample mass(g)
 D = crucible mass + Post-heated sample mass (g)
 A = crucible mass(g)
 M_c = moisture content as per cent by mass of sample

Bulk Density: 10 mL capacity pre-weighed measuring cylinders were loaded with PP and RPN samples respectively, to the graduation mark with gentle compaction until they were properly filled. The bulk density was determined from equation 4.

$$\text{Bulk density} = \frac{\text{mass of dry sample}(g)}{\text{volume of measuring cylinder}(cm^3)} \quad (4)$$

Pore Volume and Porosity: 1 g of PP and 2 g of RPN were weighed and separately poured into a beaker containing 10 mL of water. The mixtures were stirred very well and filtered. The pore volume of the samples was measured from the difference between the initial and the final volumes. The porosity was determined using the equation 5.

$$\text{Porosity} = \frac{\text{Pore volume}(cm^3)}{\text{Bulk density}(g/cm^3)} \quad (5)$$

Iodine Number: 1 g of PP sample was weighed and transferred into 250 mL capacity conical flask. 10 mL of trichloromethane (chloroform) was added to the sample and dissolved then 20 mL of wij's reagent and 15 mL of 10% potassium iodide (KI) was added and kept in the dark for 4 hours. It was thereafter titrated with 0.1 M thiosulphate solution ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$) using starch as an indicator to give a blue black colour from a yellow coloured solution. Further titration yielded a colourless solution and the titre values noted. The iodine value was calculated using the equation 6.

$$\text{iodine number} = \frac{(b - a) \times M \times 12.69}{\text{weight of sample}(g)} \quad (6)$$

Where: b = amount of thiosulphate in blank (mL)
 a = amount of thiosulphate in sample (mL)
 M = molar concentration of thiosulphate used
 12.69 = equivalent weight of iodine

Saponification Value: Two (2) grams of PP samples were separately measured into a conical flask with a capacity of 250 mL in which 25 mL of alcoholic solution of KOH was added. It was heated to boiling under reflux. After cooling, 1 mL of 1% phenolphthalein was introduced to the mixture, and the excess alcohol was titrated with 0.5 M HCl. A blank titration was also carried out without the sample. The saponification value was determined using equation 7

$$\text{Saponification Value} = \frac{(b - a) \times M \times 56.1}{\text{Weight of sample}(g)} \quad (7)$$

Where: b = amount of HCl used for blank (mL)
 a = amount of HCl used for sample (mL)
 M = molar concentration of HCl
 56.1 = Molecular weight of KOH

Fixed Carbon: Fixed was determined using equation 8.

$$\text{Fixed carbon} = 100 - (M_C + V_D + A_C) \quad (8)$$

Where: M_C = Moisture content (%); V_D = Volatile matter content (%);
 A_C = Ash content (%)

pH value: 1 gram of PP activated carbon was measured into a beaker. 100 mL of distilled water was introduced and stirred for 1 hour, the sample was left to stabilize before the pH was measured with a pH meter. The procedure was done twice.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the physical characterization of the activated carbon samples of PP and RPN are presented in this section in tables and charts.

Table 1: Characterization Results of Physicochemical Parameters of Unmodified biomasses, carbonized samples and Activated Carbon of Plantain peduncle and Raphia palm nut.

SAMPLES	PROPERTIES									
	MC	AC	VD	BD	PV	Porosity	IV	SV	FC	pH
UPP	7.5 ±2.5	10 ± 0.0	67.5 ± 0.0	0.22 ± 0.02	8.35 ±0.35	37.4 ± 2.6	202.40 ± 1.9	37.86± 1.4	15 ±1.6	6.35±0.4
CPP	10±0.0	4.75 ±0.75	94.4 ± 0.01	0.47 ± 0.01	3.1±0.1	6.58 ± 0.02	109.76 ± 1.9	114.3 ±0.7	-9.15±6.4	6 ±0.2
PPAC	7.5 ±2.5	4.25 ±0.25	62.2 ± 4.4	0.28 ± 0.01	1.7 ± 0.2	6.01 ± 1.01	320 ± 12.06	78 ±2.8	26.05±6.65	6.8±0.1
RPNAC	2.5 ±0.5	8.25 ±0.75	32.25 ±0.65	0.84 ± 0.00	3.1 ± 0.1	1.47 ± 0.05	NA	NA	57 ±1.9	NA
URPN	7.5 ±2.5	4.0 ±0.5	45.88±2.55	0.76 ± 0.01	2.05 ± 0.05	0.98 ± 0.03	NA	NA	42.62 ±5.55	NA
ASTM	3-10 max	≤ 8 max	≤ 64.7	≤ 0.925	1 -3.5	≤ 6	500 -1200	78.53	≤ 56.5	6 - 8

The physicochemical characteristics of the analyzed samples are shown in Table 1 in comparison with the ASTM maximum requirements. The graphical charts of some of these properties are also singly set out in the charts that follow. The different approach taken in this work, is the utilization of alkali activation, which has not been used in previous on these same materials. As the result shows, six properties were considered for RPN and ten were used for PP. The six parameters common to the two samples are moisture content, ash content, volatile matter, bulk density, pore volume and porosity. As shown in the table and the charts in Figure 1, moisture content, ash content, volatile matter of the PPAC fell approximately equal or within the specification range of the ASTM. The moisture content of RPNAC was nearly equal to the minimum ASTM value. The ash content was as well approximately equal to the ASTM specification while the volatile matter was comfortably within the specification range for activated carbon.

Figures 2, 3 and 4 are depictions of the variations of the bulk densities, pore volumes, and porosities of the alkali-activated carbon and other forms of the samples. All these characteristics were well within the ASTM specification range for the activated carbon of the alkali-activated carbon of PP and RPN.

Figure 1. A bar chart of moisture content, ash content and volatile matter of samples with respect to ASTM maximum standard.

In contrast to the nano-activated carbon, the results show that moisture content of PPAC was equal to that of UPP but less than CPP. Ash content was less than those of UPP (10%) and CPP (4.75%); volatile matter of PPAC was also less than those of UPP (67.5%) and CPP (94.4%). Bulk density of PPAC was slightly greater than UPP (0.22 g/mL) and less than CPP (0.47 g/mL). Pore volume of PPAC was less than those of UPP (8.35 mL) and CPP (3.1 mL). Porosity was also found to be far less than UPP (37.4 mL/g) and slightly less than CPP (6.58 mL/g).

For RPN, the activated carbon had a lower moisture content, higher ash content, lower volatile matter, higher bulk density, higher pore volume and higher porosity than the non-activated carbon. The fixed carbon for all activated carbon were greater than those of the non-activated samples; however, while the fixed carbon of PPAC was less than the ASTM standard value, RPNAC was slightly higher.

Figure 2. A bar chart of Bulk density of samples with respect to ASTM maximum standard.

Figure 3. A bar chart of Iodine value of samples with respect to ASTM maximum standard.

Figure 4. A bar chart of Porosity of samples with respect to ASTM maximum standard.

CONCLUSION

The physicochemical characterization of alkali-activated carbon and non-activated carbon from plantain peduncle (PP) and raphia palm fruit nut (RPN) was carried out. The results were compared to the standard specification range of the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) and nearly all were found to fall within the range recommended by ASTM. The results show that alkali-activated PP and RPN could be used as a good adsorbent. Further, the positive response of the non-activated portions of the samples to these test could also imply that they may effective for adsorption work depending on their surface groups and the adsorbate that would be used.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors do not have any conflicting interest

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